

METHODS AND INTERACTIVE FORMS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (NO PHILOLOGY DIRECTIONS)

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Abstract. *The article provides information about this method. Interactive (“Inter” is mutual, “act” means to act) - means interacting, talking and conducting a dialogue with someone. Interactive initiates a more multifaceted interaction of students with both the teacher and with each other, in contrast to active methods.*

Keywords: *methods and technologies, interactive, knowledge, discussion, debate, opportunity, foreign partnership, develop, innovations, priority, achievement.*

МЕТОДЫ И ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ ФОРМЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

(ДЛЯ НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ)

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация об этом методе. Интерактивный («интер» — взаимный, «акт» — действовать) — означает взаимодействие, беседу и ведение диалога с кем-либо. Интерактив инициирует более разностороннее взаимодействие учащихся как с преподавателем, так и друг с другом, в отличие от активных методов.*

Ключевые слова: *методы и технологии, интерактив, знания, дискуссия, дискуссия, возможность, зарубежное партнерство, разработка, инновации, приоритет, достижение.*

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages offer us a wide choice of learning concepts, methods and technologies, both traditional and innovative. The concept of the old school was dominated by the passive way of transferring data from teacher to student, the teacher most often expounded the finished information, demanding its reproduction later. In a more modern society, the active method of teaching a foreign language prevails. But the more advanced method is interactive. It maximally contributes to the development of communicative skills, which is the goal in itself of learning foreign languages.

The main function of a teacher in interactive classes is to direct the activities of students to the achievement of lesson objectives. The teacher, of course, develops a lesson plan (usually, these are interactive exercises and tasks during which the student studies the material).

Consequently, the main components of interactive lessons are interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The cardinal distinctive feature of interactive exercises and tasks is that, while performing them, students work on the basis of the material already studied, they are most focused on learning the new. Interactive methods allow you to move away from a monologue system of learning to a dialogue or polylogue, when students not only can freely exchange their opinions, opinions and assessments of facts, but have the right to argue with the teacher, defending their point of view, position. The interactive works when the teacher does not state the ready truths, but organizes the search and discussion by the students.

The interactive method involves the mutual learning of students, which creates a friendly atmosphere of tolerance, security, mutual support, mutual understanding. This allows us to develop the very cognitive activity through high forms of cooperation and cooperation in the process of obtaining new knowledge. 334 The essence of interactive learning is that the learning process involves all students to the maximum in the learning process, so that each participant has the opportunity to understand and reflect on their knowledge and thoughts. Hence, a huge role is given to the individualization of the knowledge of each individual in the joint activity of students in the educational process. The interchange of knowledge, thoughts, ways of action is what interaction offers. During training sessions, the development of dialogue / polylog dialogue takes place, which leads to mutual understanding, interaction, and joint solution of common, but individually valuable tasks for each participant. Interactive eliminates the dominance of both one speaker and one opinion over another.

As a result, students learn critical thinking, analyzing circumstances and solving complex problems, weighing alternative opinions, making thoughtful decisions, discussions, and communicating with other partners. For this purpose, individual, pair and group work are organized in the lessons, research projects, role-playing games are used, work is being carried out with various information sources, creative works are used. Along with the traditional (work in small groups, in couples-three, role-playing or business game) forms of work, the interactive method uses such techniques as work in rotational (replaceable) triples, carousel, unfinished offer, aquarium and others. What are the forms of interactive learning? In modern society, methodologists and practicing teachers have developed many forms of group work for teaching foreign languages.

The most widespread of them are "outer circle", "spinner", "aquarium", "brainstorming" and "debate" (the names can vary, the essence is important). These forms are effective only if the lesson discusses a problem in general, about which students have initial ideas based on previous lessons and daily life. In addition, the topics discussed should not be closed or too narrow. Now let's talk more about learning technologies. "Dialogue" - the point is that the groups find an agreed solution. The result of the work is reflected in the form of a diagram or a final text, which is then recorded in notebooks.

The methodology includes criticism of the position of another group and the search for its strong positions. Experts fix general views, and at the end of the work give a generalized response to the task, which is recorded by all. Brainstorming is a group method of generating ideas. When conducting a brainstorming session, one must proceed from the fact that there are no absurd ideas. On the contrary, it is necessary to get as many such ideas as possible. At the same time, neither the ideas nor the authors can be evaluated. "Brownian movement" - students, like molecules, randomly move around the office to gather information on this topic. "Take a position" - a statement is declared. Students approach the poster with the words "YES" or "NO". Preferably, they can explain their position. "Discussion" - educational group discussions are held on the selected problem in small groups (from 6 to 15 people) students. The educational discussion differs from other discussions in that the problem under discussion is new only for a group of people participating in the discussion, that is, the already known solution to the problem is to be found in the educational process. The search process should lead to objectively well-known, but new knowledge from the point of view of students. Form of work in groups "Interchangeable triple" - the composition of groups (triples) changes during the lesson.

“Decision Tree” - the class is divided into several groups with the same number of students. Each group discusses the issue and makes notes on the “tree” (a piece of paper or a blackboard).

Then the groups change places and write their thoughts on the trees of the neighbors. “Common project” - groups receive various tasks that cover the issue from different angles. After work is completed, reports are prepared and notes are made on the board. From these records a general project is compiled, which is reviewed and supplemented by a group of experts. “Synthesis of thoughts” - a copy of the previous method with the difference that the students make all the records on the sheets, which are then transferred to the next group. The sheet emphasizes the thoughts with which the group disagrees. The experts process the sheets and make a general report, which then discusses the class. “Search for information” - a method used to revive the dry and uninteresting material. In this case, there is a team search for information that complements the already existing (teacher lecture or homework). Subsequently, students answer questions. Answers to questions should be found in textbooks or handouts. Limited time is given to analyze information and find answers to questions. “Carousel” is a type of work that children like a lot. For this, two rings are formed: the inner and the outer.

In the inner ring, the students sit still. In the external change every 30 seconds. In a few minutes, the students speak several topics and try to convince the interlocutor in their rightness. “Aquarium” - the method consists in the fact that several students play the situation in a circle, while the others observe and analyze. Thus, at the moment a large number of methods and forms of interactive learning have been developed. But each progressive teacher can come up with their own methods of working with the class. Most of the listed interactive methods relate to cooperative learning technologies, when students unite to complete assignments, master the material and develop communication skills during discussion and argumentation of their positions.

The great advantage of this type of educational activity is that all students of the class are involved in the general work. The difficulty lies in the ability to organize the activity of students, to attach them to this type of work as permanent. The methods mentioned in 335 the article can serve as a basis for creating all new forms. Interactive creativity of the teacher and the student is limitless, this is the main advantage of interactive learning.

The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on Modern Methods of Teaching English has been limited. Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point. In planning curricular and methods. It has been suggested that an understanding of Students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations. By using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by the way introducing leading styles of teaching, teach growing generations, the system of speaking easily in these languages can be developed fully. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it. Known to us, using innovations and new pedagogical technologies are resulting well. Sometimes using same styles in teaching language may go down interests of student to language. We advise some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language. For instance: 1. Dialogical speech- in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. “Modern Methodology of Teaching English puts Speaking

in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give and opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech.” More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. 2. Student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. Reading is interactive. Reading short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek, English and American writers is very important in language learning. As a teacher of English you may apply a variety of reading strategies, analyze literary elements use a variety of strategies to read unfamiliar words and build vocabulary, prepare, organize, and present literary interpretations. 105 3. Understanding by listening- by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language. Understanding of sounding speech, in the moment of comprehension, is accompanied by intellectual activity, which includes recognizing of speech means and interpretation of the content. 4. The importance of teaching Vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in the institutes. In addition to learn new vocabulary, learner need to able to use strategies to cope with unknown vocabulary met in listening or reading text, to make up for gaps in productive vocabulary in speaking and writing to gain fluency in using known vocabulary and to learn new words in isolation. Vocabulary learning is not on end in itself. Some students learn grammar well, but in speech they meet difficulties to pronounce words. On this way we meet some questions. Maybe it is right, but in the course all aspects of teaching by new style are carrying out parallel. The theory is given, strengthens with different exercises, games, discussions in one class. We’ve spoken about groups which are got good results in following methods: 1. The level of knowledge of students and assimilating possibilities are learned and then tasks are given by this way. 2. Attracting students’ attentions is put into practice fully and none student is never stayed out of attention. 3. Students speak mainly in foreign language at the lesson, translation of unclear words isn’t told instantly, but they try to realize them with mimics. 4. Students are divided into small groups and they use these methods: “work out discussions”, “speak own opinion”, “realize together”. 5. Make opportunities to students to think and speak minds freely, and their mistakes aren’t corrected instantly, but after student speaking, they are discussed together. 6. Different grammar, phonetic and other types of games are organized. In this way roles are shared with students due to their knowledge. 7. Retell the text, variety pictures and watching short films and discussing them together, listening to news about theme and trying to realize them. We wanted to speak that the main thing in learning language is attracting students, that is to say they need motivation. It is necessary to keep activeness of student during and after lessons. The teachers around the world are always in searching about how to teach successful foreign languages to students. There are a lot of effective methods of teaching. Among the major differences between the traditional methods and the modern ones is that the modern teaching refers to “Students Centered teaching”, raising the process of teaching on such a scale that it would be not only beneficial but also interesting for learners. Good doses of such activities as Project Work, Development of Dialogues, Speech skills, Group\Pair work, whole –Class Activities, Motivating Learners, Different Games, Role-

play and Physical Activities become essential in Modern Teaching. Today teachers are facing to the following fact: Like other artisans, language teachers need both models and tools. In addition to the essential theory, aims and goals – the vision or pattern of what is to be created – they must gain through study, reflection, trial and error, and experience, the necessary expertise in using the tools essential to success in their craft. They must give serious thought to how they may lift their work to higher levels of usefulness and joy. Teachers who study and use Modern Methods of Teaching English are those who care about their own value – to self, to family, to society, to a larger community of the world. And, most, of all, they care about their students – care enough to want to constantly improve their teaching for their students’ sakes. Finally, these individuals are doers – practical achievers in their chosen profession. That’s why we are sure that our work will be of a great value and help the teachers who want to become modern and up – to date professionals. Modern Methods of Teaching English can be both challenging and demanding for teachers and students; they can also be very stimulating and rewarding. The degree to which we can adopt these approaches in our institute may well depend on willingness of our students, the proficiency of our teachers and their willingness to accept these Modern Methods, and the availability of resources within our environment. Moreover, the necessity to improve the level of education at high institutional levels is obvious nowadays. I am deeply convinced that creating collaborative atmosphere in the classroom, intellectual and informational approaches in teaching, teaching students to derive generalizations, deductive conclusion as well as developing debating abilities and individual study. “Modern Methodology of Teaching English puts Speaking in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give and opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech.” More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. Group and Pair work are so much a part of our everyday teaching routine that we can hardly pause to think before partitioning the class to tackle some particular communicative task. Group work made it possible for the teacher to devote more time to the students’ oral production, which perhaps before had not been a priority of the foreign language classroom. Another great point is Motivation. It is widely agreed that motivation has a great effect on a student’s capacity to learn. Motivation can be broken down into extrinsic and intrinsic forms. Intrinsic forms come from within the learners, who want to learn for the sake of learning. The good news for teachers is that there are many things we can do in the classroom to increase the levels of extrinsic motivation. Circle games are very 106 useful activities that involve the whole class, sitting in a circle. Many of the games recycle vocabulary and involve an element of fun. It is generally recognized today that individual learners have different learning styles, strategies and preferences. It is also generally accepted that to be effective lessons need a change of pace and focus to maintain the concentration of the learners. For both these reasons it is important that we teachers have as wide and flexible repertoire. To conclude the key strategies for teaching English classes are probably developing a positive and collaborative working atmosphere and providing a variety of work suitable for different levels. I have to say, that practically it is impossible to use one method or approach solely when aiming to teach a second language successfully. Lessons should be designed with effective methods of teaching. In this way we’ll get our goals in teaching successfully.

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